

Optimization of the design of dew-point indirect evaporative coolers with cooling and ventilation requirements

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1. Introduction

European Union policies aim to reduce and primary energy consumption and promote the integration of renewable energy sources in buildings, as an alternative to relying on fossil fuels [1]. A significant portion of current energy consumption and CO₂ emissions can be attributed to HVAC units.

Traditional air-cooling methods often involve the use of conventional HVAC units that rely on direct expansion systems [2]. Moreover, they primarily depend on electrical energy for operation.

Another approach to air cooling is evaporative cooling (EC), which involves the transfer of heat and moisture between air and water [3]. There are two primary categories of EC systems: direct evaporative cooling (DEC) operates by directly exposing air to water, leading to evaporative cooling. On the other hand, indirect evaporative cooling (IEC) involves heat and mass transfer between two distinct air streams. In IEC systems, the heat transfer surface separates these air streams, allowing for cooling without direct contact between the supply and exhaust air streams. Additionally, there are different types of IEC systems [4]: conventional IEC and dew-point evaporative coolers (DIEC). The latter can supply air between the dry bulb temperature and the dew point temperature. These systems have been extensively studied for various applications [5]. In a case study involving a residential building in China, the combination of a DIEC with a direct expansion system demonstrated significant potential for energy savings [6], achieving up to a 39% reduction compared to a direct expansion system. The integration of DIEC with a desiccant wheel [7] has enabled independent control of temperature and humidity levels.

IEC units have undergone comprehensive examination by numerous researchers in the available literature [8], with a particular emphasis on the analysis of key parameters affecting the outlet air conditions. These parameters include air temperature and humidity. The influence of different materials used in the exchanger has also been investigated in other studies [9].

Hence, utilizing an efficient air-cooling system like IEC, which rely less on electrical energy and eliminate the need for refrigerants, can present an appealing alternative to conventional air-cooling units. Evaporative coolers offer several key advantages, including their simple construction and high efficiency. The aim of this study was to determine the optimal geometric design of DIEC units in order to achieve desired cooling conditions and adhere to the European ventilation regulations [11].

2. Methodology

The energy behaviour a DIEC unit was investigated through a combination of experimental and numerical analyses under different operating conditions. The experimental analysis involved the use of a dedicated test rig, where the inlet air temperature, humidity, and air flow rate of the process flow were controlled using an air handling unit, see Fig. 1. The DIEC unit comprised a counter-flow heat exchanger, an outer casing, a hydraulic pump, and a water storage module. The exchanger consisted of polymer sheets coated with hydrophilic material on one side to retain water. Further technical characteristics of the DIEC system and of the test rig were described in [10].

Fig. 1. Layout of the test facility of the DIEC system.

A comprehensive mathematical model of the DIEC system was developed based on the ϵ -NTU method, commonly used for heat transfer rate calculations in heat exchangers. The numerical model was implemented in EES software, enabling the prediction of outlet air conditions or determination of the required length of the heat exchanger based on predefined inlet and outlet air conditions. To validate the mathematical model, 50 experimental tests were conducted, varying the inlet air temperature between 32 °C - 43

°C, inlet air humidity ratio between 6 g/kg -13 g/kg, volumetric air flow rate ratio (exhaust air flow to inlet air flow: R) between 0.2 - 0.8, and inlet air flow rate between 3000 m³/h - 4500 m³/h.

To conduct a comprehensive analysis, three case studies were carried out: an office application, a restaurant application, and an auditorium application. These cases encompassed various occupancy ratios and 3 distinct ventilation categories, namely I, II, and III. The values for the occupancy ratio and volumetric air flow rate corresponding to each ventilation category were obtained from European ventilation standards [11,12]. The specific ventilation air flow rate requirements for the DIEC system can be found in Table 1

Table 1. Case studies.

Occupancy ratio [person/m ²]	Ventilation requirements according to the European ventilation standard EN-16798-1 [m ³ /h]		
	Category III: 8 l/s person	Category II: 14 l/s person	Category I: 20 l/s person
Office: 0.1	288	504	720
Restaurant: 0.7	2016	3528	5040
Auditorium: 1.4	4320	7560	108000

For the case studies conducted, the supply air conditions of the DIEC system, outdoor air conditions and type of space being air-conditioned were kept constant, as shown in Table 2. The values of occupancy ratio, CO₂ generation rate, and area ratio were determined based on the ventilation standard [11,12].

Table 2. Supply and outdoor air conditions and characteristics of the building.

Supply air conditions	
Air temperature	18 °C
Air humidity	9 g/kg
Outdoor air conditions	
Air temperature	40 °C
Air humidity	9 g/kg
CO ₂ concentration	400 ppm
Building	
Area	100 m ²
Person ratio	7 l/s person
CO ₂ generation rate	20 l/h person
Area ratio	0.7 l/s m ²

The evaluation of the operational parameters and geometric design DIEC systems was performed based on two key performance indicators: the compactness of the system, represented by C_{DIEC}, and the coefficient of performance, denoted as COP. These parameters were obtained by Equations (1) and (2) respectively. \dot{Q}_{cool} represents the sensible energy delivered by the DIEC unit, while Vol was determined based on the dimensions of the exchange module, including length, width, and height.

$$C_{DIEC} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cool}}{Vol} \quad (1)$$

$$COP = \frac{\dot{Q}_{cool}}{\dot{W}} \quad (2)$$

3. Results

The empirical results obtained from laboratory tests were compared with the numerical results obtained through the utilization of the mathematical DIEC model. The comparative analysis focused on the variation of process air temperature, denoted as ΔT . Fig. 2 illustrates the comparison between the experimental and numerical variations in process air temperature. It is evident that there was a high level of agreement between the two, with a correlation coefficient of 0.994. This indicates that the DIEC model is highly reliable for analysing DIEC systems.

Fig. 2. Comparison of experimental and numerical ΔT results for the DIEC system.

For the office application, the results of C_{DIEC} and COP are presented in Fig. 3a and 3b. It was observed that C_{DIEC} followed a parabolic trend when \dot{V}_{SA} (or $CO_{2,ind}$) was kept constant (Fig. 3a). The highest compactness was achieved at an R value of 0.45, for a \dot{Q}_{cool} value of 4974 W. C_{DIEC} decreased for R values lower or higher than this inflection point, reaching a minimum C_{DIEC} value at R equal to 0.2. When comparing an R value of 0.45 to 0.2, there was a significant increase in C_{DIEC} , up to 76%. In terms of the volumetric air flow rate (\dot{V}_{SA}), both the cooling capacity (\dot{Q}_{cool}) and the volume (Vol) of the DIEC system increased as \dot{V}_{SA} increased while keeping R constant. However, the increase in \dot{Q}_{cool} was slightly greater than the increase in Vol, resulting in a slight overall increase in C_{DIEC} . This trend can be observed in Fig. 3a.

The COP values increased as R decreased while \dot{V}_{SA} remained constant (Fig. 3b). This was due to the reduction in \dot{V}_{EA} and \dot{W} . Conversely, for constant R values, COP slightly decreased as \dot{V}_{SA} increased (Fig. 3b), indicating that the increase in \dot{W} was greater than that of \dot{Q}_{cool} . The highest COP recorded in the study was 50.26, which was obtained for an R value of 0.2 and a \dot{V}_{SA} of 288 m^3/h . Notably, by using an R value of 0.2 instead of 0.8, the COP increased by as much as 75%. It is important to highlight that the optimal values for C_{DIEC} and COP were attained under distinct operational conditions.

Fig. 3. Results of C_{DIEC} and COP for the case studies.

For the restaurant application (Fig. 3c and 3d), the trends of the two study parameters were similar to those observed in the office application, with the exception of higher \dot{V}_{SA} values required to meet ventilation categories (as specified in Table 1). C_{DIEC} increased significantly with an increase in \dot{V}_{SA} and high constant R values, resulting in an increase in \dot{Q}_{cool} and a reduction in Vol. The maximum C_{DIEC} value was obtained at R and \dot{V}_{SA} values of 0.75 and 5040 $m^3 h^{-1}$, respectively, with a C_{DIEC} of 25195 $W m^{-3}$ (Fig. 3c). COP improved for low R values with constant \dot{V}_{SA} , reaching a maximum COP value when using an R value of 0.2 instead of 0.8. Additionally, COP improved for low \dot{V}_{SA} values, primarily due to a reduction in \dot{W} (Fig. 3d).

The patterns observed for C_{DIEC} and COP in the auditorium application were comparable to those of the restaurant application, as shown in Fig. 3e and 3f. A noteworthy observation is that when low values of the R ratio were employed, there was a greater variation in both C_{DIEC} and COP as the volumetric air flow rate (\dot{V}_{SA}) was adjusted. This finding indicates a heightened ventilation demand to meet the requirements of ventilation categories.

4. Conclusions

The optimal geometric design and operational parameters of the DIEC systems were found to be dependent on the specific type of space being air-conditioned and the ventilation category outlined in the EN 16798 European Standard. For the office application, the optimal design of the DIEC system consistently corresponded to R values of 0.45 across all ventilation categories. However, in the case of the restaurant and auditorium applications, the optimal design varied within a range of R values, specifically between 0.45 and 0.8, depending on the specific ventilation category requirements.

The optimal performance of the DIEC system occurred at low R values of 0.2 across all ventilation categories. The utilization of low R values significantly contributed to the reduction of energy consumption by the DIEC systems, thereby enhancing their overall performance. These findings emphasize the importance of selecting appropriate R values to achieve energy-efficient and effective cooling in different applications.

These results highlight the possibility of obtaining a high-performance DIEC system with a compact geometric design for buildings of various applications, complying with European ventilation regulations.

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